

Heuristic Evaluation of Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology Kenya Library and University of South Africa, Pretoria Library Websites

Onwubiko Emmanuel Chidiadi (PhD). CLN, FCAI, FSASS

Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ikwo, Nigeria

ORCID: 0000-0001-9386-4972

onwubikoemma@yahoo.com or emmabikos@gmail.com

+2348037237792

Abstract

Heuristic evaluation is a process where experts use rules of thumb to measure the usability of user interfaces in independent walkthroughs and report issues as well as everything involving collection data about the usability of any website. The work therefore is heuristic evaluation of the websites of two university libraries in Africa, the Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology Kenya Library and University of South Africa, Pretoria Library. In doing this, the Heuristic evaluation steps were adopted. These steps include, visibility of system status; match between the system and the real world, user control and freedom, consistency and standards, error prevention, recognition rather than recall. Others are flexibility and ease to use, aesthetic and minimalist design, help users recognize, diagnose and recover from errors as well as help and documentation. The evaluation covered mostly the library homepage and the library services home pages. The outcome of this evaluation apart from establishing the usability and strength also exposed areas that need improvement. As a result, it was suggested that the observations and recommendations made under each usability heuristics be corrected and implemented.

Keywords: Heuristic, Website, Evaluation, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology Kenya Library, University of South Africa, Pretoria Library

1.0. Introduction

In 1990, web usability pioneers Jakob Nielsen and Rolf Molich published the landmark article “Improving a Human-Computer Dialogue” that contains a set of principles also known as heuristics (Molich & Nielsen, 1990) which industry specialists adopted in assessing interfaces in human-computer interaction. It was seen as a fast and practical way to solving problems or making decisions. According to Interaction Design Foundation - IxDF (2024) Heuristic evaluation is a process where experts use rules of thumb to measure the usability of user interfaces in independent walkthroughs and report issues. Evaluators use established heuristics

and reveal insights that can help design teams enhance product usability from early in development. (Nielsen-Molich,1990). In user experience (UX) design explains Interaction Foundation (2016), design professional evaluators use heuristic evaluation to determine a design's/product's usability systematically. As experts, they go through a checklist of criteria to find flaws that design teams overlook.

As a guide, The Nielsen-Molich (1990) heuristics state that a system should, keep users informed about its status appropriately and promptly, Show information in ways users understand from how the real world operates and in the users' language, offer users control and let them undo errors easily. In addition, the system, should be consistent so users as not to be confused over what different words, icons, and other identifiers mean, prevent errors. In this case, the system should either avoid conditions where errors arise or warn users before they take risky actions. For instance, "Are you sure you want to do this?" messages as well as having visible information, instructions, among others to let users recognize options, actions, among others instead of forcing them to rely on memory and be flexible. To this end, experienced users could find faster ways to attaining their set goals as well as having no clutter, containing only relevant information for current tasks, providing plain-language help regarding errors and solutions and listing concise steps in lean, searchable documentation for overcoming problems.

On the advantages of Heuristic Evaluation, it is asserted that it can help highlight potential usability issues early in the design process and also act as a fast and inexpensive tool compared with other methods involving real users. To this regard, usability is defined as a measure of how well a specific user in a specific context can utilize a product/design to achieve a defined goal effectively, efficiently and satisfactorily. The outcome, in a perimeter of assessing how well a website is. Ultimately, designers usually measure a design's usability throughout the development process, from wireframes to the final deliverable as to ensuring maximum usability (Interaction Design Foundation – IxDF, 2016). Usability as it relates to man, is all about that human behavior and is built on the premise that humans are lazy, get emotional, are not interested in putting a lot of effort into, doing things and generally prefer things that are easy to do over those that are hard to do.

Ultimately, the aim of this heuristic evaluation is to determine the usability strength of two University libraries' websites, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology Kenya library and University of South Africa, Pretoria Library. A website which is also written as a web site as defined by Wikipedia (2024) is one or more web pages and related content that is identified by a common domain name and published on at least one web server. Websites are typically dedicated to a particular topic or purpose, such as news, education, commerce, entertainment, or social media. Hyperlinking between web pages guides the navigation of the site, which often starts with a home page. The Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology Kenya library is affiliated with Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology. It was established alongside the parent institution with a mission to stand out in the transformational leadership to steer the university towards achieving her vision and mission and contribute towards the social and economic development of the country (Libraries.Org, 2024). While, Jomo Kenyatta Memorial Library (JKML), University of Nairobi, Kenya which is a sister university, is located on the main campus of the University and houses information collection for

the 19 departments of the Faculty of Arts, Social Sciences as well as Engineering attesting to its diverse information collection, with a sitting capacity of about 3000. It also a total print collection of 145,000; electronic resources are cross cutting and accessible to all the University of Nairobi Library users. A breakdown of the e-collection of the university shows that E-journals are over 170,000 and E-books – 180,000 (University of Nairobi (2024)). Same cannot be said of Jomo Kenyetta University of Agriculture and Technology library that has lesser collections mainly for agricultural and technological studies though on ten campuses.

On the other hand, University of South Africa, Pretoria Library at present, is the largest academic library in Africa, is also one of the best-endowed with information resources, information technology and expert staff. The Unisa library and information services came into being in 1946 when University of South Africa introduced distance learning as a mode of tuition.

UNISA is a reputable, flexible and accessible comprehensive, open, distance and e-Learning institution that is motivating a future generation and offers internationally accredited qualifications with world-class resources. The vision is towards the African university shaping futures in the service of humanity and to find answers to Africa's educational and developmental problems. The library is known for her increasing number of electronic information resources including electronic databases, e-journals and e-books which are available to registered Unisa students and staff online 24/7, regardless of geographical location. Unisa library and information services is a signatory of the Berlin Open Access Declaration and seek to make information resources available without barriers to access. It provides the following open access digital collections: African and South African content hosted on the African Digital Library (ADL), increased visibility of Unisa research output on the Unisa Institutional Repository (UnisaIR) and Unisa Research Data Repository and Unique Digitized Archival and Heritage Collections on Unisa_Library Digital Collections. It is on record that first South African presidential library content is hosted by Unisa Library (UNISA, 2024). The general purpose of this evaluation is to establish the usability and strength of the websites as well as identify areas that need improvement as a guide to other universities building new websites as well as the olds that call for modification.

1.2. Research Objectives

The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Determine the usability and strength of the websites of two University libraries in Africa
2. Identify areas that need improvement

2.0. Methodology

In doing this evaluation, the Heuristic evaluation steps were adopted. Heuristic evaluation is all about collecting data about the usability of any website. This entails physical perusing of the websites. In this regards and following the heuristic evaluation steps, the following were assessed, visibility of system status; match between the system and the real world, user control and freedom, consistency and standards, error prevention, recognition rather than recall, flexibility and ease to use, aesthetic and minimalist design, help users recognize, diagnose and recover from errors as well as help and documentation. The evaluation covered mostly the library homepage and the library services home pages. Data collected are pictorially represented and analyzed accordingly. It is pertinent to mention that the two universities were treated individually from which, the study drew its conclusion.

3.0. Presentation and Discussion of Findings

3.1. Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology: www.jkuat.ac.ke/library

Visibility of System Status

Figure 1: Visibility of System

Going by the perused page as displayed in figure 1 above, the library homepage was well labeled showing a rundown of all the services provided by the library. The same was replicated on services homepage. The home pages contain a clear overview indicating guide to frequently requested information.

Match between the System and the Real World

Figure 2 is an expression of the match between the system and the real world. The system applied user language that can be understood by a novice. There was no form of coding that requires extra explanation. The service home page was so explicit. The overall analysis is that there is a match between the system and the real world in as observed the home page and services home page. It is pertinent to state that no provision was made for non-English speaking visitors.

Users Control and Freedom (Navigation)

Figure 3: Users control and freedom of navigation

There is no need to go through an extended dialogue while on both the home page and services home page. This is because the sites made provision for emergency exit in a situation in which a visitor to the site mistakenly chooses a system function. Every page of the site has breadcrumb

for emergency exit. On the other hand, when a user navigates into the page of the ten campus' libraries, it is as if you are entirely on a new site. This is to say, that there is a tab on the campus libraries that takes one to what looks like a different university library site. The implication is that one has to carry out so many undo processes before returning to the homepage. There is therefore, the need to create emergency exit to these libraries' pages. In other words, there should be an interface that allows immediate return to the main library homepage instead of clicking undo.

Consistency and Standard

A general review of the site shows that the layout of the university library website and the layout of services home page tab within the site followed a noticeable consistency and standard. In every page, the location of each function and feature did not change. The colour layout remained the same.

Figure 5: Same layout and colour for every page

Error Prevention

Figure 6: Error prevention indicators

In Jomo Kenyetta University of Agriculture and Technology Library, there is provision for error prevention as every online form had provision instructing a user what is required of him and to make necessary correction in case of error observed. In this situation, the form is rejected when submitted until the correction is reflected.

Recognition rather than recall

Flexibility and efficiency of use

Figure 8: Quick links at the right hand side of the site

The library site has also the site search and quick link. These allow for flexibility and efficiency, using the key words, a user can easily skip unnecessary areas and spend less time obtaining the information he desires. That is, less time is spent on navigation pages my. The fear is that the site search and quick link are not centralized as to be easily invited rather they were located off to the side of the screen at the extreme of the right hand side.

Aesthetics and minimalist design

Figure 9: Pop-up impairing users' visibility

The aesthetic and minimalist design of the library site does not depict a good work of a web designer. The web was poorly designed may be, because it is meant to attend to many users, that it is over crowded with words. Talking about the pop- up of information, this usually impairs users' visibility of the homepages. The suggestion is that this pop- ups need to be modified to enable users see the pages properly and there should be an enhancement of the aesthetic and

beauty of the site.

Help users recognize, diagnose and recover from error

The university website has an excellent error message that helps users recover and correct their errors. This was noticed while trying to fill the e- sources training survey and online registration form (see figures). The error message tells one exactly what is expected to done next. This is indeed, a good instance of the 9th usability heuristic.

Help and Documentation

It was observed in the cause of the evaluation that the library site had no help pages. This may be attributed to the assertion in the 10th usability heuristic that it is better, if the system can be used without documentation. On the other hand, it has become imperative to provide help and documentation. To this end, it is recommended that the library provides a help page at least “Ask a Librarian”.

3.2. University of South Africa: www.Unisa.ac.za/library

Visibility of System status

Figure 10: Visibility of System

The usability of the site is well guaranteed with good visibility. The home page and followed up pages were well labeled. The site has a well-designed interface that links all the services provided. One good feature that relates to heuristic feedback is “Application and Registration”

feedback. The site confirms when your application is successful. It is from the confirmation feedback that the user can go on with the “Registration” system and the real world.

Match between the System and the Real World

The university of South Africa online library had this strong match between the system and the real world. The system actually speaks users’ friendly language with words and concepts familiar to the users. Information in the system is well arranged in order of importance. There is this simplicity in the use of words. The major challenge observed was no provision for non-English users. To this, it is recommended that there should be an enhancement so as to have a place for non- English users knowing full well that the site is an online one that is supposed to be accessed by all bona-fide user regardless of language.

Users Control and Freedom (Navigation)

The library site has an easy flow interface for users. There is an ‘emergency exit’ from every page. The homepage and the services homepage are well linked for proper navigation even for a novice.

Figure 11: Navigation arrow

However, there is major observation that negates the 3rd usability heuristic that states that the users should enjoy full control and freedom of navigation (Molich & Nielsen, 1990) and that is, there is no room for quick link. This therefore calls for inclusion so that a user can quickly move to the page of need.

Consistency and Standard

The evaluator’s journey from page to page of the library site showed that the system maintained a standard and consistency in the location of each function. Each location shows that one is still

in the UNISA Library site. The site also used some conventional underlining to alert users to links. It is pertinent to mention that though conventional underlining was used to alert users to links, it was restricted to links on the left hand side of the site. To this end, this lining should be extended to the right hand side locations/ links.

Figure 12: Underlining by the left hand side to alert users to links

There is also this consistency in the use of colors on the site. Virtually every page has green, purple, oxblood and blue colors.

Error Prevention

Figure 13: Good functions preventing errors

The University of South African library site and services homepage tab within the site were built with good functions to prevent errors occurring in the first instance. From the online application to registration, there were indications of required data and where there are errors in the course of filling the form on submission. No user can submit any form twice as that is prevented through confirmation screen.

Recognition Rather than Recall

The library site objects and actions are visible to a level. The links are clearly indicated but the only area the evaluator feels should be improved on is the wordings of the library action by the left hand side of the screen that is faint in nature. The wordings should be well highlighted so that they can be easily identified by a novice. The layout of the homepage and services homepage of the university of South Africa library site makes it easier for recognition rather than recall. The homepage tab reasonably complies with the usability heuristic of recognition. All the same, the site needs to create a 'Remind me' e-mail feature knowing full well that it is opened to the outside world being an online library.

Flexibility and Efficiency Use

Using the 7th usability heuristic evaluation of flexibility and ease of use, it was observed in the course of the evaluation of the website that both the returning users and novice can comfortably and quickly use the site. It was observed that there were different box of operation for different class of persons, the able bodied and physically impaired. These are indeed accelerators designed for all and sundry. With well-defined links, a user goes straight to the tab he desires. So he can skip unwanted scene and save the time of browsing or going through all the pages. The major challenges of the site are that, there were no provisions for quick links and site search. Inasmuch as the links are there, there is still the need to create a quick link as well as site search, by so doing, much time of the users will be saved and a novice can easily and quickly obtain the needed information.

Aesthetics and minimalist Design

The evaluation of the site established one thing and that is, the library site was designed following the usability heuristic of aesthetics and minimalist design. The pages were well designed with matching colors. The homepage used a lot of white space which makes the reading of the page easier and quicker. It is a known fact, that white space helps guide the user's eyes down and across the page more quickly and easily with minimal confusion. Another good design of the site is the use of icons to represent objects and actions. The site also used lesser words and applied a picture that reveals to a novice that he is indeed on a library site. This is ultimately a focal point that grabs the user's attention.

Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from error

The membership registration has a pop-up in case of any error. The form also contains error prevention instruction indicating the compulsory data/information to be provided under "this is required". This is an excellent error message that allows a user to be mindful of the 'must' required areas to be filled. There is also re-bouncing of form if it is not well filled when it is

submitted. In this case, there is an order instructing to complete or provide particular information that is omitted. The form is not accepted until the right thing is done.

Help and Documentation

The 10th Jakob Nielsen usability heuristic of help and documentation states that though it may be better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such formation should be easy to search, focused on the user task, list concrete steps to be carried out and not to be too large. The university of South Africa library has a functional “Ask the librarian” that is located below library service by the left hand side of the screen. There is also this instruction on the ‘Ask a Librarian’ Page: “All enquires for the library can be directed to us via various channels listed on this page- Facebook, twitter, e-mail, call and by post”. In fact, the library “Help and Documentation” could be said to be near excellent.

Figure 14: Help and Documentation

There are also other help tabs like membership of the library which explains to a novice how to register to become a full bon-fide user of the library. The help and documentation may not contain all the information a user may need because of man’s insatiable nature but the truth is that the site excellently applied the 10th usability heuristic. Another important angle to it, is that the location of ‘Ask a librarian’ is very noticeable by all. All the same, there is room for improvement concerning time of call and creating a lot of email.

4.0. Conclusion

The essence of any evaluation exercise is to found out both the strengths and weaknesses of what is being evaluated and where necessary make recommendations for improvement. On

completion of the heuristics evaluation of Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology Library and University of South Africa library “Homepages and services homepages”, it was discovered that there were areas that conform with the Nielsen’s usability heuristic and there were also some of the usability heuristic that were not in conformity or are missing on the pages. As explained in the course of the evaluation report, good number of the 10 usability heuristic were applied, but there were notable weaknesses which call for improvement. To this end, it is pertinent that the observations and recommendations made under each usability heuristics be corrected and implemented.

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